

Web Accessibility aspects of HCI about MOOCs by using Automated Evaluation Tools. Systematic Literature Review.

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ABSTRACT

Accessibility principles play important function in web, and mobile platforms as well. By using these platforms, we consume various kinds of web sites and mobile applications. MOOCs are crucial in this new era to learn new skills, however, while developing such applications accessibility and usability issues arise. The main goal behind this paper is analyzing MOOC platforms and revealing accessibility level in them by using automation evaluation tools in web platform. By using HCI principles, it can be easy to evaluate MOOC platforms in terms of accessibility, and usability as well. In this research, some of the main MOOC platforms have been analyzed by automation evaluation tools. Main HCI principles have been discovered and included, such as heuristic evaluation, accessibility evaluation, cognitive research, etc.

The research aims systematic literature review; therefore, articles have been analyzed and proper solutions and approaches have been suggested for enhancing web accessibility principles for MOOC platform. Automation evaluation tool was used in the research. New and up to date WCAG principles are included in this research as well.

Keywords: Accessibility, Usability, HCI, Literature Review, Accessibility Principles, WCAG and Automation Evaluation Tools.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, accessibility has become essential for those with many types of disabilities, including speech, cognitive, vision, and so forth. Since technologies are always evolving, we should be prepared for the possibility that these individuals may experience difficulty when utilizing software and applications related to current technology. Therefore, we have conducted accessibility research for gathering possible solutions for web accessibility issues.

The main purpose of this research is conducting a systematic literature review about web accessibility by using HCI concepts, such as accessibility and usability to evaluate. As research questions, accessibility and usability principles have been analyzed, automated evaluation tools were checked, and methodologies, such as Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough have been discovered. Main WCAG 2.2 principles and their success criterion levels have been identified as well.

The significance of this research is understanding not only accessibility, but usability by implementing automated evaluation method. This approach aids in solving main accessibility and usability errors on web platforms. Two automated evaluation tools were used, WAVE and AChecker tool. Common web accessibility problems were discovered that mostly ensued at level A and AA of WCAG . For evaluation, three MOOC platforms were chosen.

While conducting the research, user and expert evaluation had been emphasized. Based on most of the research articles, the most appropriate method for evaluation is involving user and expert for evaluation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Online course platforms help us to learn new skills and offer services all over the world regardless of where we live. There are tons of platforms that exist such as Udemy, Coursera, EdX and etc. These platforms are called MOOC or Massive Open Online Course. MOOC users grow day-by-day. While creating MOOC platforms for users, companies should have to pay attention to the accessibility and usability of the platforms, and most essentially WCAG principles, which is Web Content Accessibility Guideline that covers lots of accessibility principles to make web and mobile application more accessible for the users who have some disabilities. There are lots of disabilities that we can consider, for example, cognitive, speech, visual disabilities, age related disabilities, etc. (Krolak & Zajac, 2022).

Majority of the research includes automation tools, heuristic, user-based and accessibility evaluation for accessibility and usability analysis. In the research (Krolak & Zajac, 2022), WCAG 2.1 principles was used, which are perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust. Additionally, success criteria mentioned by their levels. User group and assistive applications that they used were declared and automation tools, such as W3C validator and PowerMapper tools were used as an automatic evaluation. As a result of the research, many inconsistencies were found in Level A and AA that are deficiencies of descriptions for graphic elements and labels, keyboard controlling, skipping redundant contents, and purposes of links.

2.1 Human Computer Interaction

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the design and use of computer technology, centered on the interfaces between people and computers. It involves the study, planning, and design of the interaction between people and computers (MacDonald, et al., 2023). HCI, or Human-Computer Interaction, is a subfield of Computer Science and ID that relies on consistent interaction between humans and computer UX/UI (Shu, Xiong, & Fan, 2020). According to Szabo and Hercegf's (2022) research, HCI was first introduced in the twentieth century, and it was primarily associated with user experience. HCI prioritizes UX usability through User Centered Design (UCD), also known as Human Centered Design (HCD).

HCI examines the design of computer-related technology to improve enjoyment, usability, and productivity in computer-human interaction.

User Centered Design is a basic principle in HCI that emphasizes the significance of designing products and services with the end user in mind. It entails determining user wants, preferences, and behaviors through techniques such as interviews, observations, and usability testing. Rapid technological breakthroughs, such as touchscreens, voice recognition, gesture-based interfaces, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and wearable devices, have broadened the possibilities for human-computer interaction design.

Borthwick, Tomitsch, and Gaughwin's (2022) research found that many technological devices, web, and mobile applications, and so on do not suit people with disabilities such as visual impairment, color blindness, older people with minor visual problems, cognitive and physical problems. As a result, most worldwide businesses should not place design principles and importance second. They must be aware that this small-term revenue will result in major long-term consequences.

UX design has become important to HCI, with the goal of providing goods and services that create meaningful and engaging user experiences. This includes features including usability, beauty, utility, and satisfaction. With the rise in popularity of smartphones and tablets, HCI has moved its focus to building responsive and mobile-friendly interfaces. This covers factors like screen size, touch interactions, and mobile-specific features.

2.2 Usability

Usability is an important topic in HCI since it is concerned with making systems easy to understand and use while also decreasing the number and severity of errors. To develop a simple system with good usability, HCI specialists must be aware of the following issues (Usability.gov, 2024):

1. Efficiency: The speed at which people can finish tasks after they understand the design.
2. Learnability: The degree to which users can complete simple activities with a design when they first come across it.
3. Memorability: The ease with which people can regain proficiency with a design when they return to it after a period of inactivity.

4. Error rate, error severity, and error recovery ease are all factors affecting user behavior.
5. Contentment: The degree to which using the design is enjoyable.

In order to improve and increase system capabilities and meet users' demands and necessities, usability and HCI are increasingly becoming essential components of the system development process. From text style, fonts, layout, graphics, and color, HCI will help designers, analysts, and users identify the needs of the system; on the other hand, usability will verify whether the system is practical, visible, safe, efficient, easy to learn and remember, and provides users with a sense of fulfillment in their work. Norman and Nielsen define user experience as “all aspects of the end-user's interaction with the company, its services and products” (Zardari, Hussain, Arain, Rizvi, & Vighio, 2021).

2.3 Accessibility

Accessibility and specifically Web Accessibility are important aspects for developing web applications for people who have some disabilities. Web Accessibility guidelines are crucial for designing accessible and usable web applications. MOOC platforms should adhere to accessibility rules to ensure that every learner, regardless of their ability deficiencies, can easily access the platform to learn what they want. These are the features that should be commonly found in MOOC platforms (Sanderson, Chen, Bong, & Kessel, 2016), (Iniesto, McAndrew, Minocha, & Coughlan, 2016), (Iniesto & Rodrigo, 2016):

1. Captions: to assist deaf or hard-of-hearing learners in video content.
2. Image Descriptions: to assist visually impaired individuals by describing course components depicted in images.
3. Keyboard Navigation: to assist users who cannot use a mouse in navigating the platform using only a keyboard.
4. Universal Design Principles: MOOC platforms should be created using diverse design principles to accommodate people with disabilities.
5. Implementation of Assistive Technologies: There are various assistive technologies available that can be implemented.

6. Content Guideline System: MOOC platforms should have guideline systems to help users easily understand both the platform and course contents.

2.4 Accessibility Barriers

There are diverse amounts of Accessibility barriers in MOOC platforms, however, these barriers can vary depends on MOOC platform:

1. Deficiency of Accessible Contents: Course resources can be inaccessible for people with disabilities.
2. Inadequate Communication Tools: Communication tools on the platform may be inaccessible, causing difficulties for students with hearing or speech impairments.
3. Poor User Interface Design: The user interface may not be straightforward or simple to use, especially for students with visual impairments or cognitive disabilities.
4. Incompatibility with Assistive Technologies: The platform may be incompatible with assistive technologies such as screen readers, which are critical tools for students with specific disabilities.
5. Lack of customizing: The platform may not provide enough customizing choices to meet the different demands of learners.
6. Need for Specific Digital Skills: Learners with impairments may need additional digital skills to effectively use the platform.

2.5 Web Content Accessibility Guideline

WCAG or Web Content Accessibility Guideline are invented by W3C for designing accessible web applications. WAI or Web Application Initiative has updated WCAG guidelines to enhance accessibility in web platforms (Cao & Loiacono, 2018). It has four success criteria and each of them has their own level, which is called POUR method. Perceivable (users must be able to perceive the information being displayed), Operable (users must be able to use the interface), Understandable (users need to be able to comprehend the content and how the user interface works) and Robust (information must be accessible to consumers as technologies develop) (Akgul, 2018).

Following are the general WCAG success criteria, which mentioned in research, which created by W3C for web contents (W3C, 2023):

Table 1

WCAG success criteria and their level:

Success Criteria	Criterion Number	Title	Level	
Perceivable	1.1	Text Alternatives	A	
	1.1.1	Non-text Content	A	
	1.2.1	Audio-only and Video-only	A	
	1.2.2	Captions	A	
	1.4.1	Use of color	A	
	1.4.2	Audio control	A	
	1.4.3	Contrast	AA	
	1.4.4	Resize text	AA	
	1.4.5	Images of text	AA	
	1.4.6	Contrast	AAA	
	1.4.12	Text Spacing	AA	
	Operable	2.1.1	Keyboard	A
2.2.1		Timing Adjustable	A	
2.2.2		Pause, Stop, Hide	A	
2.4.1		Bypass Blocks	A	
2.4.2		Page Titled	A	
2.5.1		Pointer Gestures	A	
2.5.3		Label in Name	A	
2.5.7		Dragging Movements	AA	
Understandable	3.1.1	Language of Page	A	
	3.1.2	Language of Parts	AA	
	3.1.4	Abbreviations	AAA	
	3.1.5	Reading Level	AAA	
	3.2.1	On Focus	A	
	3.2.2	On Input	A	
	3.2.3	Consistent Navigation	AA	
	3.3.1	Error Identification	A	
	3.3.2	Labels of Instructions	A	
	3.3.3	Error Suggestions	AA	
	Robust	4.1.2	Name, value, role	A
		4.1.3	Status Messages	AA

WCAG 2.2 is the latest version of WCAG, and it has some differences according to WCAG

2.1. Following shows new success criteria in WCAG 2.2 (W3C, 2024):

1. Focus Not Obscured (Minimum) (AA): Ensures that when an item receives keyboard focus, it remains partially visible.
2. Dragging Movements (AA): This relates to input modalities.
3. Target Size (Minimum) (AA): Another condition for input modes.
4. Consistent Help (A) falls under the predictable guideline.
5. The input assistance guideline covers Redundant Entry (A) and Accessible Authentication (Minimum) (AA).

2.6 Web Accessibility Evaluation Methods

Developers and designers utilize a variety of evaluation methodologies for assessing accessibility across web and mobile platforms. It is not necessary to employ all of them; nevertheless, using them as a guideline for evaluation can yield better results in learning accessibility hurdles and making ideas to improve application usability for elderly persons. While researching articles about strategies for evaluating accessibility, many types of study were conducted by people from all around the world. Many researchers prefer to employ a variety of evaluation approaches, including user engagement, expert evaluation, and automated technologies. Nuñez, Moquillaza, and Paz (2019) conducted a comprehensive review of accessibility evaluation approaches. We will go over the primary methods for evaluating accessibility in the paragraphs that follow.

2.6.1 Evaluation by experts. Enhancing the accessibility in web platform demands expert involvement in evaluation procedure. Therefore, while analyzing and maintaining the accessibility in web, accessibility and usability experts should be involved.

2.6.2 Automation tools. While checking accessibility of an online web sites, there are enough numbers of automation tools to check web accessibility, such as WAVE, AChecker, etc. These tools have adopted various kinds of WCAG accessibility principles to check web accessibility. According to the research of Campoverde-Moline, Lujan-Mora and Garcia (2020), eighty percent of the analyzed papers were implemented automation tools, twelve percent of the papers were applied expert and user methods and rest of them were combined both methods. According to that research, AChecker scans individual HTML pages for accessibility standards compliance to guarantee that all users can access the information. The AChecker tool can also be configured on

your local system (Kuppusamy & Balaji, 2021). WAVE provides evaluation tools to improve accessibility of web content for those with disabilities. WAVE identifies accessibility and WCAG issues, while also allowing for human inspection of web content. WAVE's browser plugin allows for accessibility analysis of the current page (Kuppusamy & Balaji, 2021).

Besides using automation tools, we should have to know about accessibility rules based on web accessibility. Therefore, there is a web application called MyWcag4All which helps a lot to differentiate and understand rules.

2.6.3 User testing. Another notable accessibility evaluation method is user testing. This method includes users while evaluating web accessibility. While evaluation, some main methods should be used, such as Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough. These are the main accessibility and specifically usability methods for web, and mobile application evaluation as well (Park, So, & Cha, 2019).

Acosta-Vargas, Salvador-Ullauri, Perez, and Zalakeviciute (2020) employed both the heuristic method and the accessibility evaluation method in their case study. To evaluate mobile apps for air quality, accessibility assessment phases were established, combining Nielsen's usability evaluation techniques with WCAG 2.1 principles. The study's target group consisted of individuals with visual impairment limitations. Many obstacles were thus discovered, and it has been proposed that user involvement in heuristic evaluation is beneficial for evaluation.

There are various kinds of differences between Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough. Heuristic Evaluation is a practice to evaluate UI based on set of usability principles. Main significance of heuristic evaluation is defining main usability deficiencies and problems early in the design phase of an application. Heuristic evaluation maintains accessibility as well. There are some of the heuristic evaluation methods for accessibility, such as Visual Inspection, Screen reading test, Color contrast test, Keyboard navigation, etc. Cognitive Walkthrough is a usability and accessibility evaluation technique that defines task scenarios, selects groups of people with some disabilities and simulates UI.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

In this section, we will introduce methodology that is used in this research. As a systematic literature review, we have carefully reviewed enough number of articles to answer our questions in terms of accessibility aspects in MOOC platforms.

For searching articles, we have used some specific strings in IEEE Access, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, Scopus, Elsevier, Frontier, and Semantic Scholar.

Table 2

Searching States for the Research

No	State
1	("web accessibility" OR "accessibility in web")
2	("evaluation of web accessibility")
3	("accessibility")
4	("usability")
5	("usability methods" OR "usability principles")
6	("accessibility methods" OR "accessibility principles")
7	("automation evaluation tools" OR "automation accessibility evaluation")

Table 3

Research Questions

№	Research Questions
1	What are the main usability and accessibility principles?
2	Which automation tools were suits for accessibility evaluation?
3	Which methodologies are suitable for evaluating accessibility?

While evaluating accessibility, WAVE and AChecker tools were included. In the research of Campoverde-Molina, Lujan-Mora, and Garcia (2020), accessibility evaluation rating of WAVE and AChecker tools was higher. This is the main reason behind this decision that we have included these tools in this research. Besides these, many of the online resources support WAVE and AChecker tools as overly good automation evaluation tools.

4. FINDINGS

In this section, we will show our finding towards accessibility evaluation on various kinds of MOOC platforms by using Accessibility Automation tools. During evaluation process, UX experts have been involved as well. Three MOOC platforms have been evaluated in this research, and each platform identified with a simple identifier, such as MP1, MP2 and MP3.

Table 4

MOOC Platforms that were evaluated by WAVE

№	Platform	Errors	Success Criterion	Principle Number
1	MP1	Non-text Content	A	1.1.1
		Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
		Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Headings and Labels	AA	2.4.6
		Language of Parts	AA	3.1.2
2	MP2	Non-text Content	A	1.1.1
		Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
		Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Name, Role, Value	A	4.1.2
		Headings and Labels	AA	2.4.6
3	MP3	Non-text Content	A	1.1.1
		Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
		Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Name, Role, Value	A	4.1.2
		Keyboard	A	2.1.1

In table 4, three evaluated MOOC platforms have been displayed. Based on WAVE tool, sixty percent of the errors consist of A level WCAG principles, forty percent of the total errors consist

of AA level of WCAG principles. Common problems are Non-text Content, Link Purposes, Info and Relationships, Name, Role and Value, Headings and Labels.

Table 5

MOOC Platforms that were evaluated AChecker

№	Platform	Errors	Success Criterion	Principle Number
1	MP1	Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Sensory Characteristics	A	1.3.3
		Use of Color	A	1.4.1
		Keyboard	A	2.1.1
		Three Flashes or Below Threshold	A	2.3.1
		Bypass Blocks	A	2.4.1
		Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
		Multiple Ways	AA	2.4.5
		Headings and Labels	AA	2.4.6
		Language Parts	AA	3.1.2
		Consistent Navigation	AA	3.2.3
Consistent Identification	AA	3.2.4		
2	MP2	Non-text Content	A	1.1.1
		Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Sensory Characteristics	A	1.3.3
		Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
		Multiple Ways	AA	2.4.5
		Consistent Navigation	AA	3.2.3
3	MP3	Non-text Content	A	1.1.1
		Info and Relationships	A	1.3.1
		Use of Color	A	1.4.1
		Resize text	AA	1.4.4
		Images of Text	AA	1.4.5

Keyboard	A	2.1.1
Three Flashes or Below Threshold	A	2.3.1
Bypass Blocks	A	2.4.1
Page Titled	A	2.4.2
Link Purpose (In Context)	A	2.4.4
Multiple Ways	AA	2.4.5
Headings and Labels	AA	2.4.6
Language Parts	AA	3.1.2
Consistent Navigation	AA	3.2.3
Consistent Identification	AA	3.2.4

In table 5, three MOOC platforms have been displayed as well, however, in this evaluation, AChecker tool was used. According to the evaluation, forty-three percent of the total errors consist of AA level of WCAG principles. On the other hand, fifty-seven of the total errors consist of A level of WCAG principles. Based on the evaluation, Info and Relationships, Keyboard, Bypass Block, Multiple Ways, Link Purposes, Consistent Navigation, Resizing text and Images of text are common errors that have been identified on these three MOOC platforms. Therefore, paying close attention to these issues, which mostly occurred at A and AA level, are essential aspect for enhancing web accessibility.

Based on our research questions, Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough are crucial for usability testing. UCD and Expert involvement have significance in terms of accessibility evaluation methodologies.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

When it comes to those with impairments, accessibility is crucial. We need to be conscious of a wide range of interests, including advertising, social media, health care, and more. Since the majority of senior people obtain their most up-to-date information about the world from the news, we have focused our research on news-related topics in this study. They must obtain information regarding global events. They occasionally experience discomfort when learning new skills using more modern technology that is less accessible. As a result, technology, software, and applications must be accessible to humans.

In this research, we have gathered information about Accessibility and Usability, and their main principles. According to the majority of the research, Usability and Accessibility are key components for enhancing UI accessibility on web and mobile platforms. Besides these, for improving accessibility, evaluation methods have been discussed as well, and based on most of the research, using user testing and expert involvement are quite good options for evaluating accessibility. Additionally, Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough are crucial concepts for defining and evaluating usability problems. User Centered Design and Expert participation are crucial for accessibility evaluation and finding of issues related to it.

We have evaluated three MOOC platforms by using automated evaluation tools. Most of the errors occur on A level. However, the main limitation of this research is not involving users and experts for evaluation, due to unavailability of participants. Nevertheless, using automated evaluation tools have aided us to check accessibility issues on MOOC platforms. Therefore, as a future work for this research is attracting users and experts and implementing both Heuristic Evaluation and Cognitive Walkthrough methodologies. Involvement of upcoming WCAG 2.3 principles is future recommendation for this research.

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